

THEORETICAL PEARL

Termination of the simply-typed λ -calculus, revisited

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1 Introduction

You do not need a crystal ball to predict that research on the topic of termination will never end. The purpose of this pearl is to prove termination of the simply-typed λ -calculus (STLC), albeit with a twist. We start from a denotational rather than an operational semantics. Furthermore, we follow a deductive approach, aiming to discover why constructions arise the way they do, rather than pulling mathematical rabbits out of a hat. We identify three core techniques:

- (1) *defunctionalization* or firstification (turning functions into data);
- (2) *totalization* or relationalization (turning general into structural recursion); and
- (3) *strengthening* aka inventor's paradox (generalizing a proposition to simplify its proof).

We use a minimal variant of the STLC to focus on the main ideas. This allows us to present the *entire* proof, written in the dependently typed programming language Agda. The code can also be found in the accompanying material. The pearl is aimed at the level of mature graduate and beginning doctoral students.

2 Syntax

The abstract syntax of the simply-typed λ -calculus is introduced in two steps. First, the syntax of types is defined, and then the syntax of *typed* expressions. For reasons of hygiene, we use a nameless representation based on an extension of de Bruijn's notation [2].

The abstract syntax of types, often called type *codes* for emphasis, is given by

```
data Type : Set where  
  Unit : Type  
   $\_ \Rightarrow \_$  : Type  $\rightarrow$  Type  $\rightarrow$  Type
```

As we wish to focus on the essentials, we only consider a single base type and function types. The number and choice of base types has no impact on the termination proof. We let A, B, \dots range over type codes.

A typing context is represented by a backward-written sequence of types, where sequences are defined

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```

52 data Sequence (Elem : Set) : Set where
53   ⟨⟩ : Sequence Elem
54   →_ : Sequence Elem → Elem → Sequence Elem
55

```

Finally, the abstract syntax of typed expressions is given by

```

57 data _⊢_ : Sequence Type → Type → Set where
58   use : Γ , A ⊢ A
59   drop : Γ ⊢ A → Γ , B ⊢ A
60   λ_ : Γ , A ⊢ B → Γ ⊢ A ⇒ B
61   _@_ : Γ ⊢ A ⇒ B → Γ ⊢ A → Γ ⊢ B
62   unit : Γ ⊢ Unit
63

```

An element of $\Gamma \vdash A$ is an expression of type A , where the typing context Γ specifies the type of its free variables. For example, $(f\ x)\ (g\ x)$, the body of the well-known S combinator, $\lambda f \rightarrow \lambda g \rightarrow \lambda x \rightarrow (f\ x)\ (g\ x)$, translates to

```

68 S-body : ⟨⟩ , X ⇒ A ⇒ B , X ⇒ A , X ⊢ B
69 S-body = (drop (drop use) @ use) @ (drop use @ use)
70

```

In de Bruijn’s notation, variables are replaced by “pointers” into the context. For example, f is represented by **drop** (**drop use**), which refers to the second entry in the context, counting from the right starting at zero. Note that **drop** can be applied to any expression, extending de Bruijn’s original notation. For example, the variant of the S combinator that takes its arguments in reverse order, $\lambda x \rightarrow \lambda g \rightarrow \lambda f \rightarrow (f\ x)\ (g\ x)$, can be defined in one of two ways:

```

71 S1 S2 : ⟨⟩ ⊢ X ⇒ (X ⇒ A) ⇒ (X ⇒ A ⇒ B) ⇒ B
72 S1 = λ λ λ (use @ drop (drop use) @ (drop use @ drop (drop use)))
73 S2 = λ λ λ (use @ drop (drop use) @ drop (use @ drop use))
74

```

The second definition, which is slightly more compact, effectively trims the typing context, optimizing an application of the form **drop** e @ **drop** e_1 to **drop** (e @ e_1).

Remark 1. This approach to abstract syntax is sometimes called intrinsic or Church style. Logically speaking, $\Gamma \vdash A$ corresponds to the implicative fragment of Gentzen’s calculus of natural deduction [6]. The first two constructors are structural rules: **use** applies an assumption, **drop** discards an assumption, weakening the statement. The remaining constructors are introduction and elimination rules: λ introduces implication; application **_@_** eliminates it (modus ponens); and **unit** introduces “true”. In other words, programming language constructs *are* inference rules and typed expressions *are* proof trees. \square

3 Standard semantics

There are several approaches to specifying the semantics of a programming language. The denotational approach is probably the most straightforward: syntactic identities are mapped to mathematical objects. In the context of Agda, type codes are mapped to Agda types (\top is a one-element type whose only element is called *trivial*),

```

98 [[_]] : Type → Set
99 [[ Unit ]] = ⊤
100 [[ A ⇒ B ]] = [[ A ]] → [[ B ]]
101

```

typing contexts are mapped to tuple types,

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket _ \rrbracket^* &: \textit{Sequence Type} \rightarrow \textit{Set} \\ \llbracket \langle \rangle \rrbracket^* &= \top \\ \llbracket \Gamma, A \rrbracket^* &= \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket^* \times \llbracket A \rrbracket \end{aligned}$$

and expressions, elements of $\Gamma \vdash A$, are mapped to functions of type $\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket^* \rightarrow \llbracket A \rrbracket$, mappings from environments to values:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}[\llbracket _ \rrbracket] &: \Gamma \vdash A \rightarrow \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket^* \rightarrow \llbracket A \rrbracket \\ _ \square _ &: \llbracket A \Rightarrow B \rrbracket \rightarrow \llbracket A \rrbracket \rightarrow \llbracket B \rrbracket \\ \mathcal{E}[\llbracket \textit{use} _ \rrbracket] \varrho &= \textit{outr} \varrho \\ \mathcal{E}[\llbracket \textit{drop} e \rrbracket] \varrho &= \mathcal{E}[e] (\textit{outl} \varrho) \\ \mathcal{E}[\llbracket \lambda e _ \rrbracket] \varrho &= \lambda v \rightarrow \mathcal{E}[e] (\varrho, v) \\ \mathcal{E}[\llbracket e @ e_1 \rrbracket] \varrho &= \mathcal{E}[e] \varrho \square \mathcal{E}[e_1] \varrho \\ \mathcal{E}[\llbracket \textit{unit} \rrbracket] \varrho &= \textit{trivial} \\ f \square a &= f a \end{aligned}$$

The first two constructs, `use` and `drop`, manipulate the environment; λ -abstractions are mapped to Agda functions; and application is mapped to function application, written `_□_` for emphasis. The meaning function $\mathcal{E}[\llbracket _ \rrbracket]$ is compositional: the meaning of a compound expression is defined in terms of the meaning of its constituent parts. In other words, the definition is structurally recursive and hence happily accepted by Agda's termination checker.

The meaning function demonstrates that the STLC is terminating: every expression can be evaluated in a finite number of steps to a value. Now, our goal is to establish termination of the STLC, so case closed? Well, the semantics embeds the STLC into Agda. In a sense, we are leveraging on the fact that Agda is a much richer language. It is based on Zhaohui Luo's unified theory of dependent types, which has been shown to be strongly normalizing [7]. To avoid the meta-circular dependency, let us *defunctionalize* or *firstify* the standard semantics, avoiding λ -expressions on the right-hand side of the semantic equations.

4 Closure semantics

Consider again the semantic equation for λ -abstraction. In a first-order setting, we cannot continue evaluating the function body, simply because the function parameter is missing. Virtually the only option is to suspend the evaluation, storing all the necessary information so that the evaluation can be resumed as soon as the parameter becomes available. (A note on notation: the standard semantics is written with square brackets; the yet-to-be-defined closure semantics is written with angle brackets.)

$$\mathcal{E}\langle\langle \lambda e \rangle\rangle \varrho = \textit{record} \{ \textit{body} = e; \textit{env} = \varrho \}$$

The λ -abstraction is mapped to a *closure*, henceforth abbreviated by $\langle e, \varrho \rangle$, a record storing the body of the abstraction, together with the environment that defines the meaning of its free variables. Now that we have changed the interpretation of abstraction, we also need to redefine application. The definition can, in fact, be easily calculated. Consider evaluating a combination of abstraction and application: $(\lambda e) @ e_1$. On the left-hand side below, the evaluation in the standard semantics is shown (recall that `_□_` denotes function application).

154 The corresponding steps in the closure semantics are given on the right ($_ \diamond _$ denotes the
155 to-be-calculated closure application).

$$\begin{array}{ll}
156 & \mathcal{E}\ll (\lambda e) @ e_1 \gg \varrho \\
157 & = \{ \mathcal{E}\ll _ \gg: \text{application} \} \\
158 & \mathcal{E}\ll \lambda e \gg \varrho \sqcap \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho \\
159 & = \{ \mathcal{E}\ll _ \gg: \text{abstraction} \} \\
160 & (\lambda v \rightarrow \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg (\varrho, v)) \sqcap \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho \\
161 & = \{ \text{definition of } _ \sqcap _ \} \\
162 & \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg (\varrho, \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho) \\
163 & \mathcal{E}\ll (\lambda e) @ e_1 \gg \varrho \\
164 & = \{ \mathcal{E}\ll _ \gg: \text{application} \} \\
165 & \mathcal{E}\ll \lambda e \gg \varrho \diamond \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho \\
166 & = \{ \mathcal{E}\ll _ \gg: \text{abstraction} \} \\
167 & \langle e, \varrho \rangle \diamond \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho \\
168 & = \{ \text{requirement} \} \\
169 & \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg (\varrho, \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho)
\end{array}$$

170 It seems reasonable to assume that the “net effect” is the same in both semantics: evaluation
171 continues with the function body in the environment extended by the actual parameter. Hence
172 the requirement. If we abstract away from the parameter, the requirement can be satisfied by
173 setting $\langle e, \varrho \rangle \diamond v = \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg (\varrho, v)$. Let us now turn these ideas into Agda code.

174 Closures and the interpretation of types and typing contexts are defined by mutual recursion.

```

175 record Closure (A : Type) (B : Type) : Set
176   ⟨⟦_⟧⟩ : Type → Set
177   ⟨⟦_⟧⟩* : Sequence Type → Set

```

178 The semantic equations for types and typing contexts are identical to the standard semantics,
179 except for the treatment of function types.

```

180   ⟨⟦ Unit ⟧⟩ = ⊤
181   ⟨⟦ A ⇒ B ⟧⟩ = Closure A B
182   ⟨⟦ ⟨ ⟩ ⟧⟩* = ⊤
183   ⟨⟦ Γ , A ⟧⟩* = ⟨⟦ Γ ⟧⟩* × ⟨⟦ A ⟧⟩
184   record Closure A B where
185     inductive
186     pattern
187     constructor ⟨_,_⟩
188     field {Context} : Sequence Type
189       body : Context , A ⊢ B
190       env : ⟨⟦ Context ⟧⟩*

```

191 Likewise, the semantic equations for expressions are unchanged, except for the treatment of
192 abstraction and application.

```

193   \mathcal{E}\ll \_ \gg : \Gamma \vdash A \rightarrow \ll \Gamma \gg^* \rightarrow \ll A \gg
194   \_ \diamond \_ : \ll A \Rightarrow B \gg \rightarrow \ll A \gg \rightarrow \ll B \gg
195   \mathcal{E}\ll \text{use} \gg \varrho = \text{outr } \varrho
196   \mathcal{E}\ll \text{drop } e \gg \varrho = \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg (\text{outl } \varrho)
197   \mathcal{E}\ll \lambda e \gg \varrho = \langle e, \varrho \rangle
198   \mathcal{E}\ll e @ e_1 \gg \varrho = \mathcal{E}\ll e \gg \varrho \diamond \mathcal{E}\ll e_1 \gg \varrho \quad \text{-- Agda's termination checker intervenes}
199   \mathcal{E}\ll \text{unit} \gg \varrho = \text{trivial}

```

$$\gamma \diamond v = \mathcal{E}\langle\langle \text{body } \gamma \rangle\rangle (\text{env } \gamma, v)$$

A few remarks are in order.

Since the record type is recursively defined, we need to flag it either as *inductive* or *coinductive*. Perhaps surprisingly, the choice plays no rôle for the major part of the development. Inductive closures are only needed in Section 6.3, so we postpone a discussion until then. (We also need to make sure that the record constructor can be used in patterns.)

We have *defunctionalized* the standard semantics. The resulting closure semantics is morally first-order: in contrast to the standard semantics, higher-order functions are not used in any essential way. It therefore comes much closer to actual implementations of the STLC.

There is, however, a snag. While the semantics is more concrete, it lacks a defining feature of denotational semantics: compositionality. Applications are evaluated in three steps: (1) the function is evaluated; (2) the parameter is evaluated; and finally (3) the body of the function is evaluated. The last step is not structurally recursive as the evaluation function is applied to the result of the first step. This can be seen more clearly if we inline the definition of closure application:

$$\mathcal{E}\langle\langle e @ e_1 \rangle\rangle \varrho = \mathcal{E}\langle\langle \text{body } \mathcal{E}\langle\langle e \rangle\rangle \rangle\rangle (\text{env } \mathcal{E}\langle\langle e \rangle\rangle, \mathcal{E}\langle\langle e_1 \rangle\rangle) \quad (1)$$

Consequently, Agda’s termination checker rejects the definition. The purpose of the remainder of this pearl is to provide an alternative definition of $\mathcal{E}\langle\langle_ \rangle\rangle$ that is provably terminating. Of course, the semantic equations should still hold, perhaps not definitionally, but at least propositionally. It is time to unpack the next tool: *totalization*.

5 The Bove–Capretta method

Bove and Capretta have developed an ingenious method for translating a *general* recursive function into a *structurally* recursive definition [3]. The central idea is to reify the function’s call structure as an inductive datatype and to define the function using structural recursion on the call tree. This allows the actual definition (given in this section) to be separated from the proof of its termination (shown in the next section).

In more detail, a recursive function, say, $f : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$ is converted to a structurally recursive function $f' : (a : A) \rightarrow (b : B) \rightarrow \text{Dom } a b \rightarrow C$ where $\text{Dom} : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow \text{Set}$ is the type of call trees. If one can show that there is a call tree for each combination of arguments, $\text{total} : (a : A) \rightarrow (b : B) \rightarrow \text{Dom } a b$, then f can be defined: $f a b = f' a b (\text{total } a b)$. If f is a partial function, then Dom can be seen as a description of f ’s domain, hence the name.

For each case in f ’s original definition, a node constructor is added to Dom and, for each recursive call $f a_i b_i$ within that case, the node constructor has a child of type $\text{Dom } a_i b_i$.

Now, observe that the definition of the evaluation function features a *nested* recursive call, see Equation (1). Nested recursion poses a challenge. Continuing the abstract example, assume that one case contains the nested call $f a_1 (g (f a_2 b_2))$. As there are two calls, the corresponding call node has two children, one of type $F a_2 b_2$ and another of type $F a_1 (g (f a_2 b_2))$. Note that the latter type mentions f , but this function, or rather, its cousin f' is the function that we wish to define using call trees—a chicken-and-egg problem. Fortunately, there is a cure: we define F and f' by *simultaneous* recursion. Since F is a datatype and f' is a function, the definition is a lovely example of *mixed induction-recursion* [5].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{data Domain} & : (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow (\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*) \rightarrow \text{Set} \\ \text{evaluate} & : (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow (\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*) \rightarrow \text{Domain } e \varrho \rightarrow \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle \end{aligned}$$

256 The call tree for the evaluation function features five constructors, one for each language
 257 construct. The constructors `use`, `lambda`, and `unit` represent non-recursive cases.
 258

259 *data Domain where*
 260 `use` : $\forall \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma, B \rangle\rangle^*\}$
 261 $\rightarrow \text{Domain use } \varrho$
 262 `drop` : $\forall \{e : \Gamma \vdash A\} \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma, B \rangle\rangle^*\}$
 263 $\rightarrow \text{Domain } e \text{ (outl } \varrho)$
 264 $\rightarrow \text{Domain (drop } e) \varrho$
 265 `lambda` : $\forall \{e : \Gamma, A \vdash B\} \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*\}$
 266 $\rightarrow \text{Domain } (\lambda e) \varrho$
 267 `apply` : $\forall \{e : \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow B\} \{e_1 : \Gamma \vdash A\} \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*\}$
 268 $\rightarrow (c_1 : \text{Domain } e \varrho)$
 269 $\rightarrow (c_2 : \text{Domain } e_1 \varrho)$
 270 $\rightarrow \text{let } \langle e', \varrho' \rangle = \text{evaluate } e \varrho c_1 \text{ in Domain } e' (\varrho', \text{evaluate } e_1 \varrho c_2)$
 271 $\rightarrow \text{Domain } (e @ e_1) \varrho$
 272 `unit` : $\forall \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*\}$
 273 $\rightarrow \text{Domain unit } \varrho$
 274
 275
 276
 277

278 Each call node has a dependent type as the result type depends on the implicit arguments, but
 279 the type of `apply` is more dependent than the others: the type of the third subtree depends on
 280 the values of the first two subtrees.

281 Except for the additional argument, the call tree, the definition of the semantic function is
 282 unchanged (we rename $\mathcal{E}\langle\langle_ \rangle\rangle$ to *evaluate*).
 283

284 $\text{evaluate (use } \varrho) \varrho$ = *outr* ϱ
 285 $\text{evaluate (drop } e) \varrho$ (`drop` c) = *evaluate* e (outl ϱ) c
 286 $\text{evaluate } (\lambda e) \varrho$ (`lambda`) = $\langle e, \varrho \rangle$
 287 $\text{evaluate } (e @ e_1) \varrho$ (`apply` $c_1 c_2 c_3$) =
 288 $\text{let } \langle e', \varrho' \rangle = \text{evaluate } e \varrho c_1 \text{ in evaluate } e' (\varrho', \text{evaluate } e_1 \varrho c_2) c_3$
 289 $\text{evaluate (unit } \varrho) \varrho$ (`unit`) = *trivial*
 290
 291

292 Agda's termination checker now happily accepts the code as it is clearly structurally recursive.
 293 We have successfully *totalized* the closure semantics.
 294

295 **Remark 2.** Not every proof assistant supports mixed induction-recursion. In that case, one
 296 can instead *relationalize* the problematic function. Concretely, $f : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$ is turned into
 297 an inductively defined relation $R : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow \text{Set}$, the graph of f . (The graph of the closure
 298 semantics corresponds to the *big-step semantics*.)
 299

300 A nested call such as $f a_1 (g (f a_2 b_2))$ then gives rise to node with two children: one of
 301 type $R a_2 b_2 c_2$ and another of type $R a_1 (g c_2) c_1$. Since the function results are available,
 302 mixed induction-recursion is not needed.

303 If one can show that R is total, $\text{total} : (a : A) \rightarrow (b : B) \rightarrow \Sigma C (\lambda c \rightarrow R a b c)$, then f is
 304 simply the projection onto the first component: $f a b = \text{outl } (\text{total } a b)$. Practically speaking,
 305 the Bove–Capretta method is slightly more direct and hence preferred. \square
 306

6 Termination

Now, we get to the heart of the matter! We need to show that there is a call tree for every expression and every environment. Or, in more technical terms, we need to show that $\text{Domain } e \varrho$ is inhabited:

$$\text{total} : (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow (\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*) \rightarrow \text{Domain } e \varrho$$

Unsurprisingly, defining the “call tree generator” by induction on the structure of expressions does not work. The induction step cannot be carried out in the case of application, since we can only specify the first two arguments of the `apply` constructor, but not the third.

A way out of this dilemma is to *strengthen* the induction assumption, showing a stronger theorem. (The idea of generalizing a proposition so that it is easier to prove is known as the *inventor’s paradox* [9].) Concretely, for expressions of type $\Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow B$, we not only show that the evaluation of the expression itself terminates, but also that the evaluation of the resulting function body terminates. The closure semantics delays the evaluation of function bodies. In a sense, we need to undo this move: the termination of a function body is established when a closure is created, not when it is applied.

6.1 Safety and termination

There is a mutual dependency between syntactic expressions and semantic values: an expression evaluates to a mapping from environments to values; a value may contain an expression. It is therefore not too surprising that we define two predicates, one for expressions and another for values, and that these are defined by mutual recursion.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Terminates} & : (\Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^* \rightarrow \text{Set} \\ \text{Safe} & : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle \rightarrow \text{Set} \end{aligned}$$

The proposition $\text{Terminates } e \varrho$ holds, first of all, if the evaluation of e in the environment ϱ terminates. Termination is witnessed by providing a corresponding call tree.

$$\text{Terminates } e \varrho = \Sigma (\text{Domain } e \varrho) (\lambda c \rightarrow \text{Safe } (\text{evaluate } e \varrho c))$$

The witness is, in fact, a dependent pair. The first component is the desired call tree. (Inventor’s paradox: the first conjunct of the dependent pair corresponds to the original statement.) The second component additionally asserts that the result of the evaluation is *safe*. (Inventor’s paradox: the second conjunct strengthens the original statement.) Safety is a property of *values* defined by induction on the structure of type codes.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Safe } \{\text{Unit}\} & \quad u = \top \\ \text{Safe } \{A \Rightarrow B\} & \quad \gamma = \forall \{v\} \rightarrow \text{Safe } \{A\} v \rightarrow \text{Terminates } (\text{body } \gamma) (\text{env } \gamma, v) \end{aligned}$$

Values of the base type are safe. A closure is safe if the evaluation of its body terminates when a safe argument is passed to it. Finally, an environment is safe if all the entries are safe.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Safe}^* & : \{\Gamma : \text{Sequence Type}\} \rightarrow \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^* \rightarrow \text{Set} \\ \text{Safe}^* \{\langle \rangle\} & \quad \varrho = \top \\ \text{Safe}^* \{\Gamma, A\} & \quad \varrho = \text{Safe}^* (\text{outl } \varrho) \times \text{Safe} (\text{outr } \varrho) \end{aligned}$$

Here and only here we make use of the fact that the STLC is a *typed* language. Note that in untyped lambda calculus, not all terms are normalizable. Therefore, typing must play a crucial rôle in proving termination.

6.2 Termination of closed expressions

The termination proof is short and sweet. It demonstrates that evaluation always terminates, provided the environment is safe:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \textit{terminates} & : (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow \{\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*\} \rightarrow \textit{Safe}^* \varrho \rightarrow \textit{Terminates} e \varrho \\
 \textit{terminates} (\textit{use} \) \sigma & = \textit{use} , \textit{outl} \sigma \\
 \textit{terminates} (\textit{drop} e) \sigma & \textit{with} \textit{terminates} e (\textit{outl} \sigma) \\
 \textit{terminates} (\textit{drop} e) \sigma \mid (c , s) & = \textit{drop} c , s \\
 \textit{terminates} (\lambda e \) \sigma & = \textit{lambda} , \lambda s \rightarrow \textit{terminates} e (\sigma , s) \\
 \textit{terminates} (e @ e_1) \sigma & \textit{with} \textit{terminates} e \sigma \mid \textit{terminates} e_1 \sigma \\
 \textit{terminates} (e @ e_1) \sigma \mid (c , s) \mid (c_1 , s_1) & \textit{with} s s_1 \\
 \textit{terminates} (e @ e_1) \sigma \mid (c , s) \mid (c_1 , s_1) \mid (c' , s') & = \textit{apply} c c_1 c' , s' \\
 \textit{terminates} (\textit{unit} \) \sigma & = \textit{unit} , \textit{trivial}
 \end{aligned}$$

The equations merit careful study.

Producing the call tree is straightforward in the non-recursive cases. However, we also need to show that the resulting value is safe. (Inventor’s paradox: we need to install the stronger statement.) In the last case this is literally trivial. For `use`, we apply the assumption that the values in the environments are safe. In the case of λ -abstraction, we recursively call `terminates` on the body of the abstraction (as in the definition of $\mathcal{E}[\llbracket _ \rrbracket]$).

In the recursive cases, we recursively invoke `terminates` on the subexpressions, take the results apart, and build the call trees. In the case of application, we reap the harvest: the recursive calls provide us with call trees *and* proofs of safety. (Inventor’s paradox: we have strengthened the statement and hence the induction assumption. Here we require the stronger assumption.) Applying the safety guarantee for the closure to the safety guarantee for the argument, $s s_1$, yields the termination proof for the function body. Everything falls into place.

The definition of `terminates` can be seen as a nonstandard denotational semantics, mapping an environment of safety guarantees to a termination proof. In particular, the semantics is compositional. Only the type is somewhat unusual: the type of the semantic value depends on the expression and the environment.

As an intermediate result, we may conclude that the evaluation of *closed* expressions—that is, expressions without free variables—always terminates.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}\langle\langle _ \rangle\rangle & : (\langle _ \rangle \vdash A) \rightarrow \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle \\
 \mathcal{C}\langle\langle e \rangle\rangle & = \textit{evaluate} e \textit{trivial} (\textit{outl} (\textit{terminates} e \textit{trivial}))
 \end{aligned}$$

We have not yet made use of the fact that `Closure` is an *inductive* record type. Indeed, all the proofs up to this point go through without any changes if we flag `Closure` as *coinductive*. Only the next proof does require an inductive closure type.

6.3 Termination of open expressions

To prove that the evaluation of open expressions terminates, we first show that environments are safe. (This statement is not entirely trivial: an environment may contain a closure, which contains an environment, which may contain a closure ...) The proof proceeds by simultaneous induction over the structure of values and environments.

409 $safe : \{A : Type\} \rightarrow (v : \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle) \rightarrow Safe\ v$
 410 $safe^* : \{\Gamma : Sequence\ Type\} \rightarrow (\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*) \rightarrow Safe^*\ \varrho$
 411 $safe\ \{Unit\}\ u = trivial$
 412 $safe\ \{A \Rightarrow B\}\ \langle e , \varrho \rangle = \lambda s \rightarrow terminates\ e\ (safe^*\ \varrho , s)$
 413 $safe^*\ \{\langle \rangle\}\ trivial = trivial$
 414 $safe^*\ \{\Gamma , A\}\ (\varrho , v) = safe^*\ \varrho , safe\ v$
 415
 416

417 The second case is the central one. By definition, a closure is safe if the evaluation of its body
 418 terminates. We can discard this proof obligation by a call to *terminates*, but we need to show
 419 that the environment is safe. A recursive call to *safe** does the trick. The inductive definition
 420 of closures guarantees that there are no infinite chains of environments containing closures,
 421 containing an environment, containing
 422

423 **Remark 3.** The definition of *safe* and *safe** is rather subtle. Agda's termination checker only
 424 accepts it, if we *pattern match* on the closure and turn on *Axiom K*, the uniqueness of identity
 425 proofs. The record pattern is necessary so that the recursive call, *safe** ϱ , is visibly applied to
 426 a substructure of the argument. Axiom K is required as the definition relies on dependent
 427 pattern matching [4]: the record constructor $\langle e , \varrho \rangle$ is only a valid pattern for the second
 428 (the explicit) argument because the first (the implicit) argument is instantiated to $A \Rightarrow B$. \square
 429
 430

431 We are approaching the climax: a call tree exists for each combination of expressions and
 432 environments,
 433

434 $total : (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow (\varrho : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*) \rightarrow Domain\ e\ \varrho$
 435 $total\ e\ \varrho = outl\ (terminates\ e\ (safe^*\ \varrho))$
 436

437 allowing us to define the closure semantics and closure application:
 438

439 $\mathcal{E}\langle\langle _ \rangle\rangle : \Gamma \vdash A \rightarrow \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^* \rightarrow \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle$
 440 $_ \diamond _ : \langle\langle A \Rightarrow B \rangle\rangle \rightarrow \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle \rightarrow \langle\langle B \rangle\rangle$
 441 $\mathcal{E}\langle\langle e \rangle\rangle\ \varrho = evaluate\ e\ \varrho\ (total\ e\ \varrho)$
 442 $\gamma \diamond v = \mathcal{E}\langle\langle body\ \gamma \rangle\rangle\ (env\ \gamma , v)$
 443
 444

445 To summarize, we have shown that the evaluation of closed expressions terminates. The
 446 statement generalizes to open expressions, provided that closures are defined inductively. The
 447 latter condition is not only sufficient, but also necessary, as the following remark demonstrates.
 448

449 **Remark 4.** Coinductive closures allow the following corecursive definition,
 450

451 $loop : Closure\ Unit\ Unit$
 452 $Context\ loop = \langle \rangle , Unit \Rightarrow Unit$
 453 $body\ loop = drop\ use\ @\ use$
 454 $env\ loop = trivial , loop$
 455

456 constructing a closure that contains an environment that contains a closure (Just in case
 457 you wonder, the closure represents the function f defined $f = \lambda x \rightarrow f\ @\ x$.) Evaluating the
 458 call $f\ @\ unit$ using $\mathcal{E}\langle\langle use\ @\ unit \rangle\rangle\ (trivial , loop)$ of Section 4 takes a loooong time. \square
 459

6.4 Putting the pieces together

Recall the goal we set out in Section 4: we want to show that the defining equations of the closure semantics hold propositionally:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{case-use} & : \mathcal{E}\langle \text{use} \rangle \varrho \equiv \text{outr } \varrho \\
\text{case-drop} & : \mathcal{E}\langle \text{drop } e \rangle \varrho \equiv \mathcal{E}\langle e \rangle (\text{outl } \varrho) \\
\text{case-lambda} & : \mathcal{E}\langle \lambda e \rangle \varrho \equiv \langle e, \varrho \rangle \\
\text{case-apply} & : \mathcal{E}\langle e @ e_1 \rangle \varrho \equiv \mathcal{E}\langle e \rangle \varrho \diamond \mathcal{E}\langle e_1 \rangle \varrho \\
\text{case-unit} & : \mathcal{E}\langle \text{unit} \rangle \varrho \equiv \text{trivial}
\end{aligned}$$

In fact, all the equations hold definitionally, with the notable exception of the second but last one. Both sides normalize to the same invocation of *evaluate*, except that the call trees are not definitionally equal. Now, one would hope that evaluation does not depend on the supplied call tree. This is, indeed, the case. In fact, call trees are unique: for every combination of expressions and environments, there is at most one call tree:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{unique} & : \forall \{e : \Gamma \vdash A\} \{\varrho : \langle \Gamma \rangle^*\} (c d : \text{Domain } e \varrho) \rightarrow c \equiv d \\
\text{unique } (\text{use}) (\text{use}) & = \equiv\text{-reflexive} \\
\text{unique } (\text{drop } c) (\text{drop } d) & \\
\text{rewrite unique } c d & = \equiv\text{-reflexive} \\
\text{unique } (\text{lambda}) (\text{lambda}) & = \equiv\text{-reflexive} \\
\text{unique } (\text{apply } c_1 c_2 c_3) (\text{apply } d_1 d_2 d_3) & \\
\text{rewrite unique } c_1 d_1 & \\
\text{rewrite unique } c_2 d_2 & \\
\text{rewrite unique } c_3 d_3 & = \equiv\text{-reflexive} \\
\text{unique } (\text{unit}) (\text{unit}) & = \equiv\text{-reflexive}
\end{aligned}$$

For the proof of *case-apply*, we then simply invoke congruence and uniqueness.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{case-apply} & : \forall (e : \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow B) (e_1 : \Gamma \vdash A) (\varrho : \langle \Gamma \rangle^*) \\
& \rightarrow \mathcal{E}\langle e @ e_1 \rangle \varrho \equiv \mathcal{E}\langle e \rangle \varrho \diamond \mathcal{E}\langle e_1 \rangle \varrho \\
\text{case-apply } e e_1 \varrho & = \\
& \equiv\text{-congruent } (\text{evaluate } (e @ e_1) \varrho) (\text{unique } (\text{total } _ _) (\text{apply } _ _ _))
\end{aligned}$$

In the next section, we come full circle and return to the standard semantics, seeing *case-apply* in action.

7 Equivalence of standard and closure semantics

We have introduced two different semantics for the simply-typed λ -calculus, a higher-order and a first-order one. The question naturally arises how they are related. Clearly, for expressions of functional type we obtain different answers, but one would expect that the semantics agree on base types. (Our base type has only one element so the question is moot. However, as we have already noted, the choice of base types is completely orthogonal to the termination proof.) For functional values we require that related arguments are taken to related results. The following definition captures these requirements.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Related} & : \{A : \text{Type}\} \rightarrow \llbracket A \rrbracket \rightarrow \langle A \rangle \rightarrow \text{Set} \\
\text{Related } \{\text{Unit}\} & \quad u_1 u_2 = u_1 \equiv u_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Related } \{A \Rightarrow B\} f_1 f_2 = \\ \forall \{a_1 : \llbracket A \rrbracket\} \{a_2 : \langle\langle A \rangle\rangle\} \rightarrow \text{Related } a_1 a_2 \rightarrow \text{Related } (f_1 \square a_1) (f_2 \diamond a_2) \end{aligned}$$

The relation is defined by induction on the structure of type codes. Note that f_1 is an Agda function, while f_2 is a closure. They must behave identically; the only way to observe a function's behaviour is to apply it, using $_ _$ for functions and $_ \diamond _$ for closures. As an aside, a type-indexed relation that satisfies the last clause is called *logical* [8].

Likewise, two environments are related if elements at corresponding positions are related.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Related}^* : \{\Gamma : \text{Sequence Type}\} \rightarrow \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket^* \rightarrow \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^* \rightarrow \text{Set} \\ \text{Related}^* \{\langle \rangle\} \varrho_1 \varrho_2 = \top \\ \text{Related}^* \{\Gamma, A\} \varrho_1 \varrho_2 = \text{Related}^* (\text{outl } \varrho_1) (\text{outl } \varrho_2) \times \text{Related} (\text{outr } \varrho_1) (\text{outr } \varrho_2) \end{aligned}$$

Then one can show that the meaning functions take related environments to related values.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{correct} : \forall (e : \Gamma \vdash A) \rightarrow \forall \{\varrho_1 : \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket^*\} \{\varrho_2 : \langle\langle \Gamma \rangle\rangle^*\} \\ \rightarrow \text{Related}^* \varrho_1 \varrho_2 \rightarrow \text{Related} (\mathcal{E} \llbracket e \rrbracket \varrho_1) (\mathcal{E} \langle\langle e \rangle\rangle \varrho_2) \\ \text{correct } (\text{use } _) \varrho = \text{outr } \varrho \\ \text{correct } (\text{drop } e) \varrho = \text{correct } e (\text{outl } \varrho) \\ \text{correct } (\lambda e _) \varrho = \lambda r \rightarrow \text{correct } e (\varrho, r) \\ \text{correct } (e @ e_1) \{\varrho_2 = \varrho_2\} \varrho \\ \text{rewrite } \text{case-apply } e e_1 \varrho_2 = (\text{correct } e \varrho) (\text{correct } e_1 \varrho_2) \\ \text{correct } (\text{unit } _) \varrho = \equiv\text{-reflexive} \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to implicit arguments, the definition is (almost) identical to the definition of the standard semantics. In the second but last case, we need to rewrite by *case-apply* as the semantic equation for application only holds propositionally. The proof that the interpretations of $e @ e_1$ are related then involves the same reasoning steps as in the derivation of closure application (see Section 4), where we aligned the closure semantics to the standard semantics.

8 Conclusion and further reading

Termination of the simply-typed λ -calculus is a standard topic in courses on the foundations of programming languages. The original proof by Tait [10] and most modern presentations, with the notable exception of [1], are based on a small-step semantics. As a result, the proofs are quite technical and not very attractive. In contrast, our termination proof consists of only about 50 lines of Agda code and might even be suitable for presentation in a lecture.

The work by Altenkirch and Chapman [1] is close in spirit to ours: they show decidability of conversion for a simply typed λ -calculus with explicit substitutions and $\beta\eta$ -equality, a system which is *not* strongly normalizing. They relationalize the evaluation function resulting in a big-step semantics, see Remark 2. (Their *entire* Agda sources consist of about 1000 lines of code, which is why the paper contains a mixture of formal definitions and semiformal arguments.) In a way, our approach can be seen as a simplification of their work, for a simpler calculus and aiming for a more modest goal. That said, they deserve full credit for proposing the marriage of the Bove-Capretta method with logical relations. Three cheers for them!

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